

REEMPHASIZING THE KENOTIC-CHRISTOLOGICAL IMPETUS OF DR. FELIX WILFRED AS THE NEED OF THE TIME

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Abstract: Religio-political despotism often permeates human society, dehumanising even the post-secular era. Conflicts, nurturing these, have caused irreparable damage to humanity, abetting anti-pro sentiments vis-à-vis a section of society. Wars thus waged have led to mass-slaughters of innocent people across the globe. A sense of empathy overlooks the clamour of its victims. India, with its many redeeming figures and philosophies, requires a perspective-renewal, inspired by the insights of Dr. Felix Wilfred on the self-emptying of Jesus Christ, fostering a respectful coexistence.

Keywords: Felix Wilfred, Christology, Incarnation, Kenosis, Church, Social Mysticism, Prophetic Anger.

INTRODUCTION

Extremism is principally associated with religion; nevertheless, it surfaces in politics, ideology, and ethnicity¹ throughout human history. Some of the glaring examples in the past are the burning of witches and the Crusades by the Church, the anti-Buddhist revival in Hinduism, and the

¹ Cf. Martin Odermatt, *Der Fundamentalismus: Ein Gott eine Wahrheit eine Moral? Psychologische Reflexion* (Solothurn – Düsseldorf: Benziger Verlag, 2. ed., 1994).

Armenian and Rwandan genocides, the political and cultural holocausts under Nazism in Germany, etc., and the more recent massacre in the northern Nigeria, the radicalization of Buddhism in Myanmar and Sri Lanka, the wars between Ukraine and Russia, Israel and Hamas, Israel and Iran, the unresolved violence in the North-Eastern State of Manipur, India, etc.

With the growing statistics of non-religious belief-systems in the postmodern Europe, religion seems to lose its importance. Christianity faces a pluralistic environment as it strives to reassert itself in a global market of cosmo-vision and religious diversity, proclaiming the uniqueness of Jesus Christ. It is relevant to note that Christianity once claimed its absolutism on the ground of Jesus' uniqueness. Now the question arises: Is it now practical and relevant? Could this approach to religious absolutism be replaced by Jesus' uniqueness in his self-emptying? The self-emptying love of God in Jesus Christ encourages us to critically evaluate whether the life and teachings of the historical Jesus serve as a guiding standard in a pluralistic society like India.² In Felix Wilfred, we endeavour to rediscover the uniqueness of Jesus Christ in his kenotic Incarnation and the unsurpassable gesture of God's love for humanity.

A genuine quest for Christology does not only arise from an academic pursuit, but also from a personal encounter with Jesus Christ and the specific context. Thanks to 'the rigorous scientific methodology' acquired in Europe, Felix Wilfred realized the "need to begin from scratch and engage in a theological [Christological] praxis and thought that reflected more closely the actual context of the people, their history, philosophy, culture and tradition."³ For this, the interpretation of Jesus Christ should emerge from the Indian context,

² Cf. David Hadeley Jensen, "The Emptying Christ," *Studies in Interreligious Dialogue* 11/1 (2001): 5-24.

³ See the Preface to Felix Wilfred, *On the Banks of Ganges: Doing Contextual Theology* (Delhi: ISPCK, 2005), x.

and should also consider the economically and socially impoverished condition of the common Indian populace.

Furthermore, it is indispensable to understand the religious consciousness of the people for an effective ‘Christologization.’ Wilfred draws our attention and challenges us, “so that we may understand and approach the mystery of Jesus with a certain innovativeness and originality.”⁴ Hence, he outlines three key necessities: (i) the quest to discover Jesus Christ within the Indian context,⁵ (ii) to interpret Jesus Christ in the Indian context as he interpreted God by observing the lives and struggles of people in his time,⁶ (iii) and to present Jesus Christ whose divine identity is connected to human identity.⁷

Hence, kenosis could be a starting-point of an Indian ‘Christologization,’ because Felix Wilfred’s kenosis is not just an abstract concept, but rather a social commitment.⁸ He sees self-emptying as leading to self-transcendence. In the Indian context, this self-transcendence has two dimensions: one through spiritual discipline, attaining the zenith of God and self-realization, and the other involves a deep-rooted commitment to society. In both realms, Wilfred’s Christological viewpoints introduce a degree of relativism, implying that self-emptying and self-transcendence are not exclusive to Jesus Christ, but

⁴ Felix Wilfred, “Jesus-Interpretations in Asia: Fragmentary Reflections on Fragments,” *East Asian Pastoral Review* 43/4 (2006): 334. In this regard, see also Jacob Parappally, “The Development of Indian Christological Reflections in Dialogue with Other Religions,” in *Christus und die Religionen: Standortbestimmung der Missionstheologie*, ed. Markus Luber et al. (Weltkirche und Mission, Band 5; Regensburg: Verlag Friedrich Pustet, 2015), 198-218.

⁵ Felix Wilfred, *Beyond the Settled Foundations: The Journey of Indian Theology* (Madras: Department of Christian Studies, 1993), 19-69.

⁶ Felix Wilfred, *From the Dusty Soil: Contextual Reinterpretation of Christianity* (Madras: Department of Christian Studies, 1995), 137-175.

⁷ Felix Wilfred, “Liberation in India and the Church’s Participation,” in *Leave the Temple. Indian Paths to Human Liberation*, ed. Felix Wilfred (Faith Meets Faith Series; Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 1992), 175-197.

⁸ Felix Wilfred, *For a Socially Engaged Faith* (Delhi: ISPCK, 2024), 78.

are universal spiritual dimensions also found in other religious traditions.⁹

The kenotic Christology finds its roots in Phil 2:6-11, where the concept of Kenosis occurs literally. However, theologically, the Gospels are rich with a kenotic theology.¹⁰ Felix Wilfred provides various contexts for understanding the kenotic Christology in India. According to him, ‘Christologizing’ involves our response to Jesus Christ, who enables us to respond to people from every stratum, while imitating the mind of Christ (Phil 2:2-5)—a new paradigm of service, emulating the *One* who “humbled himself” (Phil 2:8).

Felix Wilfred delineates the process of this kenotic Christological praxis: (i) praxis-oriented involvement in a concrete situation, understanding the reality exemplified

⁹ Such a reflection of Wilfred seems to be a relative approach. Wilfred helps us consider the profound significance that Asian traditions hold. Here, his approach is inclusive in adopting what is found meaningful in others and pluralistic in entering into a broader spectrum of dialogue. So that there is no argument of absolute claim, but rather a humble enquiry into what others want to say. For him, kenosis is a universal longing, but Christ’s self-emptying in social commitment makes it unique. However, the kenosis of Christ could also be described as of the absolute kind, God’s full self-emptying to become man, and hence, unique.

¹⁰ The meaning of kenosis is understood from both non-biblical and biblical perspectives. Given the extensive academic research that has been conducted, we will not repeat it here. Jesus expressed an attitude of self-emptiness on various occasions, directly and indirectly. (i) It needs to be deciphered to understand the context in which Jesus expressed it to himself: when Jesus received baptism (Mt 3:14-15); God revealed his wisdom to the innocents (Mt 11:25); Jesus kept his Messiahship secret for a definite time (Mt 20); the purpose of the coming of the Son of Man (Mt 20:28; Mk 10:45); the teaching on the greatest commandment (Mt 22:34-40; Mk 12:28-34; Lk 10:25-28); showing compassion (Mt 9:36); Jesus prays for his persecutors (Lk 23:34); (ii) and as an exhortation to his followers: at the time of persecution (Mt 5:11); concerning anger (Mt 5:23-24); concerning retaliation (Mt 5:38-42; Lk 6:29-31); love for enemies (Mt 5:43-48; Lk 6:27-36.32-36); while exercising the mission of the Lord (Mt 10:8b); the cross and self-denial (Mt 16:20; Mk 8:34-9:1; Lk 9:23-27); forgiveness is an attitude of self-emptying (Mt 18:21-22); concerning greatness (Mt 18:1-5; Mk 9:33-37; Lk 9:46-48); the cost of discipleship (Mt 10:34-39; Mk 14:27); being fruitful (Jn 12:24); love commandment (Jn 13:34; 15:12-14). However, considering the historical circumstances, culture and tradition of Jesus’ time, every ministry that Jesus carried out was an act of his self-emptiness.

by Jesus; (ii) engagement with the socio-political realities affecting the poor and underprivileged; (iii) and supporting the victims, who are the “underside of history.”¹¹

Thus, ‘Christologizing’ in India, can be envisioned by immersing oneself or ‘incarnating’ in the Indian socio-political and economic landscape. An Indian incarnation occurs due to an exigency, an existent unjust situation. The Christian act of this immersion as a Christological approach envisions the emergence of a just society as a form of Incarnation (body of Christ) that, in a sense, contextualizes the idea that “the Word became flesh” (Jn 1:14).

1. WILFRED’S INTERPRETATIONS OF INCARNATION

1.1 Social Mysticism and the Mystery of the Incarnation

Felix Wilfred underlines the need for “a social mysticism that permeates everyday life, surpassing superficial adjustments and delving into the realms of mindset, values, and methods, and the very approach to social engagement.”¹² Christianity highlights the confession of faith in Jesus Christ and the social commitment he exemplified in personal and social transformation. In his humanity, Jesus enabled human beings to encounter the divine and grasp divine mysteries, for he revealed to the world the true nature of the invisible God. Jesus opened the ways to encounter *this invisible* God in one’s personal experience and by engaging oneself in human relationships. Social mysticism unfolds the expression of true love for one’s neighbour through service as “a visible expression of love for God.”¹³ Social mysticism is the path that leads to love of God and love of neighbour within “a communal and social dimension ... for the welfare and wholeness of all.”¹⁴ Emphasizing social

¹¹ Cf. Felix Wilfred, *Asian Dreams and Christian Hope. At the Dawn of the Millennium* (Delhi: ISPCK, 2003), 274-277.

¹² Wilfred, *For a Socially Engaged Faith*, 17.

¹³ *Ibid.*, 18.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, 19.

mysticism, Christians should be aware of the vulnerability of the oppressed masses and the marginalized individuals, while recognizing their own helplessness.

Another dimension of social mysticism is the need to forgo personal gains in favour of social interests. It serves as a means to liberate people, helping them realize their full humanity and motivating them to engage in social commitments. In a reciprocal relationship, social mysticism considers every social commitment as a “sacred duty”¹⁵ to offer one’s resources for the benefit of others. In this context, James H. Cone states: “[T]he political and the cultural situation would require a reinterpretation of Jesus Christ so as to be effective in communicating precisely what the biblical Jesus represents.”¹⁶ The biblical Jesus offers us inner freedom to engage ourselves in his mission of embracing humanity. Freedom is the realization of fullness of life in oneself that motivates commitment, connecting one’s spirituality to the rest of creation. As Wilfred emphasizes, “Freedom serves as the pivotal concept that bridges the realms of spirituality and society.”¹⁷ However, the inner freedom enables one to break free from self-imposed confinements and become a catalyst for active social transformation. This freedom empowers individuals to work towards the liberation of others.¹⁸

1.2 Incarnation Discloses the Future History

The foundation of the Christian faith rests on God’s revelation through Jesus Christ. The apostolic proclamation that began

¹⁵ Ibid., 20.

¹⁶ James H. Cone, “A Black American Perspective on the Asian Search for a Full Humanity,” in *Asia’s Struggle for Full Humanity: Towards a Relevant Theology*, ed. Virginia Fabella (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 1980), 183.

¹⁷ Wilfred, *For a Socially Engaged Faith*, 21.

¹⁸ Ibid. While Wilfred discusses social mysticism, it extends beyond the narrow-mindedness of the caste system, religion, and tribe, as well as the sociocultural and economic-political circumstances and even bureaucracy that confine personal growth and social transformation; see *ibid.*, 17-22.

after Jesus's resurrection serves as a historical record. Wilfred examines the Incarnation and Kenosis as portrayed in Scripture, viewing them as an expression of selfless service. He maintains that the Incarnation should not remain merely within the realm of dogma; it must accompany God's opening of a new *marga*—a path to be followed in freedom. He asserts, "Incarnation is not a closure of history, but a disclosure to the future course of history."¹⁹ This disclosure of history facilitates transformation, both personal and collective, as we interpret the Old Testament as a story of God's ongoing presence throughout history.

History is dynamic. The book of Exodus reveals the nature of God, who guides the course of history, while also revealing his unceasing presence within it. Wilfred interprets the historical event of the Exodus as more political than theological.²⁰ Wilfred points out,

[H]istory becomes the meeting place of God. This history is dynamic and comprises political processes, economic dealings, social interactions, and cultural creations. God becoming flesh means that God is involved in God's self-manifestation in politics, economy, society, culture, and so on, which constitute human existence.²¹

The future of history hinges on the present condition of society. History is never stagnant in the present; it is progressive, leading to a future.

1.3 Christology is Doing Missiology

Drawing on the theological motifs of the two streams of traditional Christologies, the Christology from above and the Christology from below, Wilfred nomenclatures them as *descending missiology* and *ascending missiology*.²² These

¹⁹ Felix Wilfred, *Religious Identities and the Global South: Porous Borders and Novel Paths* (Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2021), 102.

²⁰ Wilfred, *For a socially Engaged Faith*, 77.

²¹ *Ibid.*, 99.

²² *Ibid.*, 64.

terms capture the traditional expressions of Christology. By presenting these formulations, Wilfred aims to reemphasize the contrasting limitations in understanding Jesus Christ. In descending missiology, Jesus Christ is proclaimed as a unique redeemer worthy of worship, whereas in ascending missiology, the focus is on the portrayal of the historical Jesus, whose life and death on the Cross holds a profound significance. He asserts, "A genuine missiology will interpret God through the experience of human, social, and ecological realities and interpret these in the light of God."²³ The mission involves effective evangelization as proclaimed by the earthly Jesus Christ, whose mission is fulfilled through proclamation, dialogical engagement, and social commitment. This dialogical engagement broadens the interpretation of the mission "from the real life-stream of today."²⁴ He further elucidates that the

Mission is to contribute to the realization of the purpose of God for the whole of humanity in history. Concretely we experience this in Jesus Christ. In him we see how this purpose of God is really open, universal and without barriers, embracing the whole of the human race and its future destiny as a transformed humanity.²⁵

Driven by ideology or personal philosophy, one is persuaded to pursue goal-driven actions, even against the current. Jacob Parappally states that the Christian understanding of God is not an abstract concept, but rather what Jesus introduced to the world is the longing of the Asian people.²⁶ The mission involves realizing one's participation in the life, death, and resurrection of Jesus Christ. The mission is not merely a duty, but is the realization of "the inner

²³ Ibid., 66.

²⁴ Ibid., 67.

²⁵ Felix Wilfred, "Once Again ... Church and Kingdom," *VJTR* 57 (1993): 15.

²⁶ Jacob Parappally, "The Challenging Newness of Jesus Christ in the Context of Religious Pluralism," *Cristologia e Missione oggi* (Rome 2001): 117-126.

enlightenment-experience.”²⁷ It has a universal character because its beneficiaries are all. The mission embodies both engagement and discipleship.

1.4 Incarnation as Kenosis

God, by revealing himself in Jesus of Nazareth, unveiled a mystery of kenosis to the world. The one who existed in the status of God did not regard his highness but descended to earth to live as one with humanity. This concept is closely related to the Indian notion of an *avatāra*,²⁸ a divine figure descending to save humankind. The Incarnation in Christianity reveals the mystery of kenosis, which teaches us that God relinquishes his absolute claim to power, becoming one with the vulnerable and revealing himself as a servant. Unless God reveals and manifests himself in human form, he cannot disclose humanity and his servanthood revealed in Jesus Christ.

God reveals another dimension of divinity – goodness – by humbling himself to the level of human beings, not merely as a servant available to humanity, but even to the point of death (Mk 10:45), a death that unveils a new horizon of God’s nature. In his human nature, God empties himself entirely, so that the mystery of the Incarnation is manifested beyond human understanding. This mystery reveals that God can endure suffering.²⁹ God’s suffering is unique in its redemptive purpose for humanity. The Incarnation signifies God’s acceptance of humanity and identification with it. Thus, “The Word became flesh and dwelt among us” (Jn 1:14) represents a unique expression of the divine mystery. The realization of this mystery is concretely demonstrated in the life and mission

²⁷ Wilfred, *On the Banks of Ganges*, 211.

²⁸ Noel Sheth, “Hindu Avatāra and Christian Incarnation: A Comparison: I and II,” *VJTR* 67 (2003): 181-193, 285-302.

²⁹ Cf. Wilfred, *Sunset in the East*, 151. Thomas Weinandy, *Does God Suffer?* (Notre Dame: University of Notre Dame, 2000), describes how God is understood in relation to suffering from the perspective of Greek philosophy and the early Fathers of the Church.

of Jesus (Lk 4:18-19),³⁰ where the Incarnation is the revelation of God's physical presence in the world; it reaches its climax only when understood within every historical and cultural context, where human life is encountered in the light of the Scripture (esp. cf. Mt 11:2-6; Mk 1:1-8; Lk 4:16-19).

1.5 Kenosis: Perpetual Incarnation

Wilfred highlights that the mystery of the Incarnation, which we confess in our faith, occurred for the sake of humankind. In this act, God revealed his inner self both as God and as a servant to human beings (Phil 2:6-11) by taking on human flesh.³¹ The Incarnation, as a kenotic act, fully manifests in the embrace of various forms of vulnerability. The covenant experience of the Israelites represented an absolute relationship with God in history. God, who communicated with the prophets from afar, took on human form in flesh and blood and entered the world to be with the people. He became a human being in the flesh, so that he could experience every human feeling within human nature.

Therefore, in Jesus of Nazareth, God entered into human history not as a distant deity but as 'Immanuel,' who would engage in every sphere of human life. God's entry into the human world signifies God's presence in history. The Gospels proclaim the God of history in Jesus Christ, whose involvement was felt in every aspect of life, as a violation of human dignity can arise from any distorted social sector. Thus, Wilfred says, "God becoming flesh implies God's self-manifestation in politics, economy, society, culture, and so on, all of which constitute human life and history."³² The

³⁰ Cf. Wilfred, *Sunset in the East*, 302.

³¹ Wilfred, *For a Socially Engaged Faith*, 10.

³¹ *Ibid.*, 96-97.

³² *Ibid.*, 77. The words of Leonardo Boff go well with the thought of Wilfred. Boff says, "A Christology that proclaims Jesus Christ as the Liberator seeks to be committed to the economic, social, and political liberation of those groups that are oppressed and dominated." Leonardo Boff, *Jesus Christ the Liberator: A Critical Christology of Our Time* (London: SPCK, 1980), 266.

metaphysical understanding of God needs to be grounded in the earthly realm, where God's presence is experienced through his self-emptying participation.

2. SOCIAL COMMITMENT AS THE SOUL OF KENOSIS

2.1 The Kenotic Mystery of the Cross amidst Dehumanization

The Church in India exemplifies the mystery of the Cross by engaging in active social transformation and pastoral activities, drawing considerable inspiration from the contextualized theology of Latin America.

In Latin America, profound reflections on the mystery of the cross amidst dehumanization and oppression have led to the perception of the poor and marginalized as a crucified people. This perspective views Christian involvement as an effort to alleviate the suffering and injustice faced by the crucified, providing an antidote to social indifference and apathy.³³

Wilfred presents Jesus Christ to people and challenges them in his name. His challenges are not only to address secular perspectives but also to radically confront ecclesiastical undertakings. Although Wilfred has great appreciation for the Church's engagement through its caritative activities, he believes the Church needs to venture much more. The option for the poor, the displaced, and the deprived represents the signs and symbols of kenosis, where the Logos must convey the redeeming message. Commenting on Wilfred's reflection, Calvin D'Costa articulates: "Wilfred wants to start with and prioritize the poor: the Dalits, women the marginalized and economically exploited. If the church is not fighting for liberation for the poor it has lost its salt and will not be a real voice in India for India."³⁴

³³ Wilfred, *For a Socially Engaged Faith*, 10.

³⁴ Cavin D'Costa, "Inculturation, India and Other Religions, Some Methodological Reflections," *Studia Missionalia* 44 (1995): 133.

The Church becomes a beacon in society only when it bears the cross through every social struggle. The liturgy of the sacraments finds its fullness in sharing in the suffering of the marginalized. The kenosis of Christ was an event of brokenness, and in his brokenness, he revealed the resurrection of another life in the world. Thus, Wilfred emphasizes that the Indian Church must take up the cross, risking its name and losing its identity to save the lives of the weak and the marginalized. At this juncture, Samuel Rayan's reflection is apt; one who takes up this task also becomes one with them in "sharing the insult."³⁵ Breaking one's body is not just charity, but rather to be open to 'an insult' to one's own image. Thus, the cross becomes heavy, and flesh is torn apart. One who has denied the heaviness of ego only can lift the cross, for it requires self-denial (cf. Mt 16:24-26).

2.2 Prophetic Kenosis and Political Encounter

Kenosis necessitates engagement in the political sphere as one of the challenging areas to advocate for the voiceless and stand with those deprived of their rights. For Wilfred, "The Church's prophetic mission calls for involvement in the political realm, especially when state and its organs increasingly go against moral order, human dignity and rights. Evangelization without prophetism is a body without a soul."³⁶ Recent years have witnessed the Church's voice in support of the poor and the marginalized. It is the Church in India that has penetrated every breadth and labyrinth, knowing the pulse of the subaltern groups.³⁷

³⁵ Samuel Rayan, "Outside the Gate, Sharing the Insult," in *Leave the Temple: Indian Paths to Human Liberation*, ed. Felix Wilfred (Faith Meets Faith Series; Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 1991), 125-145.

³⁶ Wilfred, *For a Socially Engaged Faith*, 72.

³⁷ Cf. Francis X. Clooney, "Reengaging the Classical Traditions in the Light of Popular and Subaltern Hinduism: Extending Felix Wilfred's Reconsiderations of Hindu-Christian Relations," in *Negotiating Borders. Theological Explorations in the Global Era: Essays in Honour of Prof. Felix Wilfred*, ed. Patrick Gnanapragasam – Elisabeth Schüssler Fiorenza (Delhi: ISPCK, 2008), 418-421.

Wilfred observes that economic marginalization, power manipulation, and authoritarianism have increasingly throttled the poor masses. The need for ecclesial engagement is to end every form of marginalization. Although structural development and an inflow of investments are arising, Wilfred notes, “marginalization of the masses from the political and economic mainstream and their growing powerlessness have shattered the hopes of a democratic and just society which India wanted to be at the time of Independence.”³⁸ Against this background, Wilfred highlights the necessity of public theology: “Public theology delves into the profound political significance of the Christian faith and emphasizes the vital role of faith in offering prophetic insights during the critical times.”³⁹

Prophetic kenosis unites the oppressed in solidarity and raises their awareness of human rights and dignity. The Church ventures into this empowering medium, drawing on the Cross as the model of God’s power reflected in the Church that stands by the powerless.⁴⁰ In claiming to stand with the underprivileged and the despised in society, the primary duty of the Church is to proclaim the truth (Jn 14:6) and stand for truth by defending and safeguarding against all forms of oppression.⁴¹

Gripped by the social experience, prophetic kenoticism dares to confront injustice. Injustice warps society. Wilfred sees prophetic anger “as a medium to bridge the gulf that divides the lofty realities and the misery of the prevailing situation.”⁴² A question arises: how does prophetic anger

³⁸ Felix Wilfred, “Harbingers of Hope: Action Groups in India Today,” *VJTR* 49/11 (1985): 542.

³⁹ Wilfred, *For a Socially Engaged Faith*, 6. See also, Felix Wilfred, “*Fratelli Tutti* as an Exercise in Subaltern Public Theology,” *VJTR* 85 (2021): 246-268.

⁴⁰ Cf. Felix Wilfred, “A Power that Pulls: Reflections on the Church and the Exercise of Power,” *Jeevadhara* 19/109 (Jan 1989): 70-71.

⁴¹ Felix Wilfred, “Church – a Pillar of Truth,” *Jeevadhara* 14/81 (May 1984): 191.

⁴² Felix Wilfred, “Prophetic Anger and Sapiential Compassion: Grappling with Evil Today,” *Concilium* (2009/1): 34; “Listening to the World: Prophetic Anger and Sapiential Compassion,” Paper presented in the Conference at United Theological Seminary, New York, April 2013 and published in *Buddhist-Christian Studies* 34 (2014): 63-66.

become kenotic? It involves addressing malevolent forces that inflict suffering on the innocent and working to prevent them from causing grievous harm. The speeches of prophets in the Old Testament show occasions when they became angry (cf. Ex 32:49; 1 Sam 15:24-30). Anything that contravened the statutes and ordinances of YHWH prompts the prophets to express their fury.

2.3 Kenosis – the Renunciation of Self-seeking

Wilfred reflects on the passion and death of Jesus on the cross as an example of renouncing self-seeking. The offering of Jesus, to the point of death, is the highest act of freedom. It represents the utmost expression of love and service for the sake of humanity. Jesus neither imposed his suffering on others nor escaped from it; instead, he accepted it freely and willingly, bearing the cross himself. His prayer on the Mount of Olives reveals his freedom to accept and yield to the will of his Father: “Father, if you are willing, remove this cup from me; yet not my will but yours be done” (Lk 22:42). Here, Wilfred urges to contemplate alongside Paul as he wrote to the Corinthians about the scandal and foolishness of the cross (1 Cor 1:23-25).⁴³ The life of Jesus and his dedication to his Father’s will led him to a tragic death, yet his death was not the culmination of everything. His resurrection is the reward granted to him by his Father. The selfless love he revealed on the cross was demonstrated through his words and actions. He said there is no greater love than giving one’s life for one’s friend (Jn 15:13).

Such a principle from Jesus was applied not only to his disciples but also to the entire human race. The work of Jesus was the visible expression of God, as he revealed to the Prophet

⁴³ Cf. Wilfred, *Zum Verständnis Jesu Christi im heutigen Indien*, 85. Wilfred says the scandal of the cross needs to be explained by the historical existence of Jesus, which means his mission. The whole mission of Jesus was kenotic. The Cross became the culmination of God’s kenotic act in Jesus Christ. The mission command of Jesus was the mission command of the early prophets, who underwent shame and torture.

Isaiah that he did not send angels or messengers but his presence to save his people in his love, redeeming them (Isa 63:9). He taught them that he stands with humanity and is also ready to face suffering as they do. Being God, he could have destroyed his enemies, but he did not. Yet he is “a God merciful and gracious, slow to anger, and abounding in steadfast love” (Ex 34:6). The selfless love of God revealed in Jesus Christ reflects the primordial action of his heavenly Father.⁴⁴

2.4 Kenosis as Compassionate Reconciliation

For Wilfred, compassion encompasses all the virtues that guide one towards reconciliation, accompanied by forgiveness and repentance. A compassionate attitude is truly a manifestation of grace. It calls for justice and peace.⁴⁵ Compassion arises from wisdom. For Wilfred, compassion “is not a sign of weakness but of strength”⁴⁶ that characterizes wisdom. Wisdom perceives reality in its entirety. Compassion opposes evil and stands with the truth. The holistic vision of compassion is viewed through the lens of human suffering. This attitude of compassion leads one to reconciliation and forgiveness because God is merciful and regards both virtuous and vice-ridden actions alike (Lk 6:36). Kenosis reaches its zenith in the one who remained silent in the face of torture and excruciating pain. Despite all this, his words were: “Father forgive them ...” (Lk 23:34). It is through compassionate kenotic reconciliation that peace and justice can be established.⁴⁷

We find that Jesus’ kenotic mission aims to reveal the true face of humanity and its sacredness. From a Christian perspective, humanity is seen through the lens of sacramentality because human beings are considered sacred

⁴⁴ Cf. Wilfred, *On the Banks of Ganges*, 151-152.

⁴⁵ Felix Wilfred, “Cultural Resources for Peace and Reconciliation,” *Concilium* (2013/1): 92-93.

⁴⁶ Wilfred, *Prophetic Anger and Sapiential Compassion*, 28. Felix Wilfred, “Listening to the World: Prophetic Anger and Sapiential Compassion,” *Buddhist-Christian Studies* 34 (2014): 63-66.

⁴⁷ Cf. Wilfred, *Prophetic Anger and Sapiential Compassion*, 35-37.

in the sight of God. Reconciliation is a virtue when it sprouts from a humble heart, bending towards the other, offering forgiveness. The receiver accepts forgiveness gladly because it leads to internal openness, which in turn serves a radical transformation. Thus, forgiveness in Jesus is the outstanding reflection of kenosis and compassion. Compassion enables one to see the face of the other and imbues them with a sense of sacredness. The other is also an object of divine encounter. Object does not mean nonsignificant, but the sacramentality of God's imprint on that person. The compassionate attitude of Jesus Christ teaches us the sacramentality of humanity, that the dwelling of God's presence is an invisibly imprinted image of God.⁴⁸

2.5 Kenosis as Collaboration and Appreciation

Kenosis creates space for respect and mutual understanding of cultures, traditions, and various worldviews. It fosters a relationship between openness and new learning. As people encounter God in their own way or experience a Divine Presence, openness is required from the disciples of Jesus Christ, as these divine experiences enrich people of other faiths and traditions. Collaboration and appreciation are essential in the modern world for those aiming to address societal suffering. In the words of Wilfred, "The collaboration among religions for the advancement of peoples is all the more urgent today since the world religions are playing an important role in shaping the social life and determining the political destinies of nations."⁴⁹ Just as the Church has its identity in the world, so must every local Church recognize its role in the liberating work for the people as a sign of the

⁴⁸ Similar thought can also be found in Siluvai Pillai Johnson, *Experiencing the Sacramental Presence of Jesus in the Human Community through the Affirmation of the "Other": A Comparative Study of the Insights of Felix Wilfred and David N. Power* (Dissertation Thesis, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, 2008), 63-69.

⁴⁹ Felix Wilfred, "World Religions and Christian Inculturation," *India Theological Studies* 25/1 (March 1988): 22.

Kingdom of God. The Word became flesh for a distinctive purpose: to establish God's reign, where all people have equal rights to participate. Thus, Wilfred states:

The message of the Kingdom of God, the central concern of Jesus, was about [hu]man's life and problems, his[/her] struggle and groanings, hopes and expectations in his[/her] everyday existence under the rule of God. Precisely because it concerns humanity and its problems, the message of the Kingdom, like Wisdom, has no barriers [Lk 14:13; cf. Mt 25:31-45]. The Kingdom of God cannot be the possession of any one people, just as life and God are not the possession of one people.⁵⁰

The Church, as the body of Christ and a community of people, serves as an instrument for liberation. Liberation begins when local churches collaborate closely with other local organizations dedicated to the emancipation of the marginalized. For this reason, the Church must inculturate itself in every dimension of local life. An inculturated Church understands the needs of the poor. Wilfred acknowledges the Church's significant work, which has been undertaken intensively for several decades. Collaboration and appreciation also facilitate entry into the "culture, traditions, values and institutions"⁵¹ of the community where the Church offers its humanitarian service. In inculturation, the Church incarnates itself amidst the people.

CONCLUSION

Pluralism challenges absolutism; it enables one to transcend the limitations of the prescribed belief system and seek the efficacious work of the Word in every tradition and culture. God is related to every culture, history, and people. Religious pluralism is not an obstacle to preaching the kenosis of Jesus Christ. The methodology of proclamation must remain

⁵⁰ Felix Wilfred, "A Matter of Theological Education: Some Critical Reflections on the Suitability of 'Salvation History' as a Theological Model for India," *VJTR* 48/11 (Nov 1984): 556.

⁵¹ Wilfred, "World Religions and Christian Inculturation," 26.

authentic to declare the self-emptied Jesus Christ. For that reason, the Church cannot but “proclaim the cross of Christ as the sign of God’s all-embracing love and as the fountain from which every grace flows” (NA 4). Christianity does not claim triumphalism over other religious traditions or any political ideology; rather, it bears witness by being crucified with Christ (Gal 2:20), despising the shame associated with it (Heb 12:2). Simultaneously, Christians can boast of it (Gal 6:14) as a sign of peace (Col 1:20) and acknowledge the universal significance of Jesus Christ in his unique expression of self-giving love.

What we have discussed is only a portion of Felix Wilfred’s reflections. Understanding Wilfred’s reflections critically reveals that the suffering of Jesus and the pain experienced by ordinary, poor people in rural India are similar; the difference lies in the absence of a wooden cross. The agony and mental torment endured by millions in India are akin to that of Jesus Christ. For some, the suffering begins even at birth. Its cause is the caste system, poverty, and other related problems. Jesus Christ shares in the suffering of these people. His suffering represents solidarity with theirs. For him, the Cross was a reality; for millions of suffering individuals, the Cross serves as a symbol of suffering. However, many endure a virtual crucifixion in both body and soul.

Wilfred sees the Church as the kenotic symbol of Christ; it enables the world to understand the true meaning of the Incarnation. It helps one to perceive God’s presence in history with a universal spirit. Christian faith in the Incarnation embraces all humans without barriers, recognizing them within their social context and individual traits. The Church reveals the mystery of the Incarnation to those unfamiliar with the mystery of God’s identification with humanity. Thus, the Incarnation is a radical commitment to and active participation in the lives of people with whom Christians share their own lives.